

Reactions of Phenylpyruvic Acid Oxime with Cations

Mohan Katyal and R. P. Singh

The use of phenylpyruvic acid oxime in the estimation of copper has been reported by the authors' earlier. The present communication deals with the reactions of the oxime with other cations and the I. R. spectrum of the copper-oxime complex with a view to providing an additional evidence in favour of the structure suggested earlier¹.

The reactions of phenylpyruvic acid oxime with different cations have been studied at different pH's. The results are recored in Table I.

TABLE I

Cation.	Taken as.	Remarks.
Li ⁺	LiNO ₃	No precipitate.
Na ⁺	NaCl	Do
K ⁺	K ₂ SO ₄	Do
Cd ²⁺	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	White precipitates are obtained at salt pH. In highly acidic medium (HNO ₃), however, no precipitates are obtained. Under these conditions, even the copper complex undergoes partial decomposition and hence separation of copper from these cations is not possible.
Hg ²⁺	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	
Bi ³⁺	Bi(NO ₃) ₃	
Ce ⁴⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ Ce(NO ₃) ₆	Precipitates obtained in all these cases were ignited in an attempt to weigh them as respective oxides. Quantitative results are not obtained.
ZrO ₂ ⁺	ZrOCl ₂	
Th ⁴⁺	Th(NO ₃) ₄	
W ⁶⁺	Na ₂ WO ₄	
Co ²⁺	CoSO ₄	Light buff-coloured precipitate in case of cobalt and white precipitate with bluish tinge with nickel ions are obtained. Precipitation has not been found to be quantitative.
Ni ²⁺	NiSO ₄	
UO ₂ ²⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	No immediate precipitation occurs. Precipitates are, however, obtained on keeping the mixed solution of uranium and thorium etc. for some time. Precipitation is quicker in presence of ceric and thorium salts due to coprecipitation phenomenon.

The blue copper complex of phenylpyruvic acid oxime decomposes at 204°. Its I. R. spectrum was taken to provide a supporting evidence for the structure already proposed.¹ The spectrum of the solid blue copper complex was taken in nujol mull using Perkin Elmer Infracord.

1. Katyal and Singh, *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, 31, 373.

Infrared studies of complexes of carboxylic acid anions by Sen *et al.*² reveal that the

C=O stretching frequency of the group $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C}-\text{O}-\text{M} \end{array}$, in which M is a cation, is rather close to that for the free carboxylate ion and much farther from that of a relatively covalent car-

boxyl group, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C}-\text{OH} \end{array}$. In the present case, the peak at 1670 cm^{-1} may well be interpreted

in terms of $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C}-\text{O}-\text{M} \end{array}$ type of linking. This value is much further from 1750 cm^{-1} , meant for covalent carboxyl group. The frequency 1670 cm^{-1} is, however, still higher than the

usually reported value for $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C}-\text{O}-\text{M} \end{array}$ group and this rise may be attributed to co-ordination of the nitrogen atom of the oxime group to the metal atom. Electrostatic interactions and also covalent bonding have generally been found to affect the frequencies. Hence the interpretation of I.R. spectrum favours the already suggested structure (I) of copper-oxime complex and the possibility of structure (II) is ruled out.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF DELHI,
DELHI-6.

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